

Synthesis and Characterisation of Mercury(II) Complexes with some Schiff Bases

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Fortyfive complexes of mercury(II) of the type $HgX_2.SB$ (where $X=Cl, Br, I, SCN$ and NO_2 ; SB =Schiff base derived from diamines and aromatic carbonyl compounds) have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, conductivity, ir and X-ray photoelectron spectral data.

ALTHOUGH a large number of Hg^I and Hg^{II} coordination compounds have been reported¹, the Hg^{II} complexes with Schiff base ligands are relatively less known. We report here the synthesis of the Hg^{II} complexes with various bidentate Schiff base ligands derived from benzaldehyde, acetophenone or cinamaldehyde and different diamines prepared from HgX_2 as a starting material, and characterised by physicochemical and spectroscopic data.

Experimental

The aromatic carbonyl compound (2 mmol) and the diamine (1 mmol) were mixed in methanol and refluxed for ~3 h. Tlc suggested complete conversion of the starting materials to the Schiff base. The mercury compound (HgX_2) (1 mmol) was then added and the mixture refluxed for ~3 h. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and air-dried.

The microanalysis of the complexes were carried out at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Conductance measurements in DMF were made at room temperature using a Digisun electronics conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra of ligands and the complexes were recorded in nujol and KBr respectively on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer.

The X-ray photoelectron spectra were recorded on a VG Scientific ESCA-3 MK II electron spectrometer. The MgK_{α} X-ray line (1253.6 eV) was used for photoexcitation. The $Cu2p_{3/2}$ ($E_b=932.8 \pm 0.2$) and $Au4f_{7/2}$ ($E_b=83.8 \pm 0.1$) lines were used to a calibrate the instrument and $Ag3d_{5/2}$ ($E_b=368.2$) was used for cross-checking². All the spectra were recorded using the same spectrometer parameters of 50 eV pass-energy and 4 mm slit-width. The reduced full width at half maximum (FWHM) at $Au4f_{7/2}$ ($E_b=83.8$ eV) level under these conditions was 1.2 eV.

The powdered sample was mixed with high purity silver powder to reduce the charging effect. A thin layer of such a sample was pressed on a

gold metal gauze which was welded to a nickel sample holder. The $Ag3d_{5/2}$ level ($E_b=368.2$ eV) obtained from this sample was sharp and did not show any observable shift. Thus the charging of the sample if at all present was negligible³. The spectra were recorded in triplicate in the region of interest. In the most cases the binding energies were reproducible within ± 0.1 eV. The usual least-squares fitting procedure of determining peak position, line width and area was used.

Results and Discussion

Equimolar addition complexes of HgX_2 ($X=Cl, Br, I, SCN$ and NO_2) with the following Schiff base ligands have been prepared: SB_1 =bisbenzaldehyde ethylenediamine, SB_2 =bisbenzaldehyde 1,3-diaminopropane, SB_3 =bisbenzaldehyde-O-phenylenediamine, SB_4 =bisacetophenone ethylenediamine, SB_5 =bisacetophenone 1,3-diaminopropane, SB_6 =bisacetophenone-O-phenylenediamine, SB_7 =biscinamaldehyde ethylenediamine, SB_8 =biscinamaldehyde 1,3-diaminopropane and SB_9 =biscinamaldehyde-O-phenylenediamine.

All these complexes (Table 1) are stable with high melting points and insoluble in common organic solvents except DMF and DMSO. Microanalytical and conductance data (below than $60 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) suggest that the complexes are non-electrolyte⁴ with composition of $HgX_2.SB$.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF $HgX_2.SB$ COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
	C	H	N	X=Cl, Br	Hg
$Hg(SCN)_2.SP_1$	39.0 (39.1)	2.6 (2.8)	10.0	—	36.2 (36.3)
$Hg(SCN)_2.SB_2$	40.1 (40.2)	3.0 (3.1)	9.6 (9.8)	—	35.2 (35.4)
$Hg(SCN)_2.SB_3$	44.1 (44.0)	2.4 (2.6)	9.2 (9.3)	—	33.4 (33.6)
$Hg(SCN)_2.SB_4$	41.2 (41.3)	3.2 (3.4)	9.4 (9.6)	—	34.2 (34.5)
$Hg(SCN)_2.SB_5$	42.2 (42.4)	3.6 (3.7)	9.2 (9.4)	—	33.4 (33.7)

(Table 1 contd.)

Hg(SCN) ₂ .SB ₆	45.6 (45.8)	3.0 (3.1)	8.6 (8.9)	—	31.6 (31.9)
Hg(SCN) ₂ .SB ₇	43.6 (43.7)	3.2 (3.3)	9.1 (9.2)	—	33.0 (33.1)
Hg(SCN) ₂ .SB ₈	44.6 (44.7)	3.4 (3.5)	9.2 (9.0)	—	32.2 (32.4)
Hg(SCN) ₂ .SB ₉	47.6 (47.8)	3.1 (3.0)	8.6 (8.5)	—	30.4 (30.7)
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .SB ₁	34.2 (34.2)	2.6 (2.8)	10.2 (10.0)	—	35.6 (35.7)
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .SB ₂	35.4 (35.5)	3.0 (3.1)	9.6 (9.7)	—	34.6 (34.9)
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .SB ₃	39.2 (39.4)	2.5 (2.6)	9.1 (9.2)	—	33.0 (33.2)
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .SB ₄	36.6 (36.6)	3.2 (3.4)	9.4 (9.5)	—	34.1 (34.0)
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .SB ₅	37.6 (37.8)	3.4 (3.6)	9.2 (9.3)	—	33.0 (33.2)
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .SB ₆	41.4 (41.5)	3.0 (3.1)	8.4 (8.8)	—	31.6 (31.5)
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .SB ₇	39.1 (39.2)	3.0 (3.2)	9.0 (9.1)	—	32.8 (32.7)
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .SB ₈ [¶]	40.1 (40.2)	3.4 (3.5)	8.6 (8.9)	—	32.0 (32.0)
Hg(NO ₃) ₂ .SB ₉	43.5 (43.6)	3.1 (3.0)	8.2 (8.4)	—	30.3 (30.3)
HgCl ₂ .SB ₁	37.6 (37.8)	3.0 (3.1)	5.4 (5.5)	13.8 (14.0)	39.2 (39.5)
HgCl ₂ .SB ₂	39.0 (39.0)	3.2 (3.4)	5.2 (5.3)	13.5 (13.6)	38.6 (38.4)
HgCl ₂ .SB ₃	43.1 (43.2)	2.6 (2.8)	5.1 (5.0)	12.8 (12.7)	36.2 (36.3)
HgCl ₂ .SB ₄	40.2 (40.3)	3.6 (3.7)	5.2 (5.2)	13.2 (13.2)	37.6 (37.4)
HgCl ₂ .SB ₅	41.4 (41.5)	4.1 (4.0)	5.1 (5.1)	12.8 (12.9)	36.2 (36.4)
HgCl ₂ .SB ₆	45.1 (45.2)	3.2 (3.4)	4.6 (4.8)	12.0 (12.1)	34.2 (34.4)
HgCl ₂ .SB ₇	42.8 (42.9)	3.4 (3.5)	5.2 (5.0)	12.8 (12.7)	35.6 (35.8)
HgCl ₂ .SB ₈	43.8 (43.9)	3.6 (3.8)	4.6 (4.8)	12.2 (12.3)	34.8 (34.9)
HgCl ₂ .SB ₉	47.2 (47.4)	3.1 (3.2)	4.6 (4.6)	11.5 (11.6)	33.0 (33.0)
HgBr ₂ .SB ₁	32.1 (32.2)	2.4 (2.6)	4.5 (4.6)	26.6 (26.8)	33.4 (33.6)
HgBr ₂ .SB ₂	33.2 (33.4)	2.8 (2.9)	4.4 (4.5)	26.0 (26.2)	32.4 (32.8)
HgBr ₂ .SB ₃	37.1 (37.2)	2.6 (2.4)	4.2 (4.3)	24.6 (24.8)	31.2 (31.3)
HgBr ₂ .SB ₄	34.4 (34.6)	3.3 (3.2)	4.4 (4.4)	25.4 (25.6)	32.0 (32.1)
HgBr ₂ .SB ₅	35.6 (35.7)	3.5 (3.4)	4.2 (4.3)	25.2 (25.0)	31.2 (31.4)
HgBr ₂ .SB ₆	39.1 (39.2)	3.0 (2.9)	4.1 (4.1)	23.6 (23.8)	29.6 (29.8)
HgBr ₂ .SB ₇	37.1 (37.0)	3.1 (3.0)	4.2 (4.3)	24.4 (24.6)	30.6 (30.7)
HgBr ₂ .SB ₈	38.2 (38.0)	3.2 (3.3)	4.2 (4.2)	24.0 (24.1)	30.0 (30.2)
HgBr ₂ .SB ₉	41.4 (41.3)	2.6 (2.8)	4.1 (4.0)	22.8 (22.9)	28.6 (28.8)
HgI ₂ .SB ₁	27.6 (27.8)	2.2 (2.3)	4.1 (4.0)	36.6 (36.8)	29.1 (29.0)
HgI ₂ .SB ₂	28.8 (28.9)	2.4 (2.5)	4.0 (3.9)	36.2 (36.0)	28.2 (28.4)
HgI ₂ .SB ₃	32.4 (32.4)	2.0 (2.1)	3.8 (3.7)	34.2 (34.4)	27.2 (27.3)
HgI ₂ .SB ₄	30.2 (30.0)	2.3 (2.7)	3.6 (3.8)	35.2 (35.3)	27.8 (27.9)
HgI ₂ .SB ₅	30.6 (30.8)	2.8 (2.9)	3.6 (3.8)	34.4 (34.6)	27.0 (27.3)
HgI ₂ .SB ₆	34.2 (34.4)	2.4 (2.6)	3.6 (3.6)	33.0 (33.1)	26.0 (26.1)
HgI ₂ .SB ₇	32.4 (32.3)	2.4 (2.6)	3.6 (3.7)	34.1 (34.2)	27.0 (27.0)

(Table 1 contd.)

HgI ₂ .SB ₈	33.4 (33.3)	2.8 (2.9)	3.6 (3.7)	33.4 (33.5)	26.4 (26.5)
HgI ₂ .SB ₉	36.2 (36.4)	2.4 (2.5)	3.4 (3.5)	32.0 (32.1)	25.2 (25.3)

The ir bands observed at 1610–1670 cm⁻¹ of all the ligands and complexes are assigned to ν_{C-N} vibration⁵. The ligand ν_{C-N} bands around 1610 cm⁻¹ in the ligands shifted to 1635–1670 cm⁻¹ in the complexes due to an increase of bond order on coordination⁶. The bands at 420–390 and 255–210 cm⁻¹ in the complexes may be assigned to ν_{Hg-N} and ν_{Hg-Cl} ^{7,8} respectively. The thiocyanato complexes showed bands at about 2100 (CN), 710 (CS) and 415 cm⁻¹ (NCS), which clearly indicate coordinated S-bonded thiocyanato group^{9,10}. The nitrate complexes showed a monodentate bonding mode of nitrate in the complexes^{9,10}.

The binding energy data of Hg4p_{1/2,3/2} N1s and Xnp photoelectron peaks for the HgX₂, HgX₂.SB₁, HgX₂.SB₂ and HgX₂.SB₃ complexes showed that Hg4p_{1/2,3/2} BE value is highest in Hg(SCN)₂ and decreases in the order, Hg(SCN)₂ > Hg(NO₃)₂ > HgCl₂ > HgBr₂ > HgI₂ (Fig. 1). It may further be noted that Hg4p BE value in the starting material

Fig. 1 Hg4p_{1/2} photoelectron peak in HgX₂ (X=SCN, NO₃, Cl, Br, I)

HgX₂ is higher than that (having same X) in HgX₂.SB complexes. From these XPS data one can conclude that the Schiff base ligands are coordinated to mercury metal ion. It is further noted that Hg4p, N1s and Xnp BE is maximum for HgX₂.SB₁ and minimum for HgX₂.SB₃. Using Siegbahn's generalisation¹¹ it is concluded that

maximum effective positive charge on N1s, Xnp and Hg4p is for HgX₂.SB₁ and minimum for HgX₂.SB₃ complexes. The decreasing order of effective positive charge on Hg4p_{1/2,3/2}, N1s and Hg4p is HgX₂.SB₁ > HgX₂.SB₂ > HgX₂.SB₃. It is clear that phenyl group of Schiff base increases electron density on nitrogen, halogen and mercury metal ion, and electron density in these complexes decreases in the order, HgX₂.SB₃ > HgX₂.SB₂ > HgX₂.SB₁.

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